

maximum yield of 20.3% was obtained when the reactants were heated at 140° for 6 hr in presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride

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References

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A New Method for Resolution of Racemic forms of α -Amino acids and Related Compounds

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It has now been discovered that racemic forms of α -amino acids, their esters and in general, compounds containing an active amino group (e.g. threoamine) can be resolved by interaction with simple quinone molecules under suitable conditions to give monosubstituted quinonoid products of which the *d*-form separates completely during the reaction period leaving the *l*-form in solution.¹

X = H or halogen

Verification of the above results was accomplished by interaction of *p*-quinones with pure *d*- or *l*-forms and comparison with the above results using thin layer chromatographic technique, mps, mixed mps and optical rotation measurements. The reactions were carried out with *dl*-alanine, *dl*-valine, *dl*-isoleucine, *dl*-aspartic acid, and *dl*-tryptophane, and *d*-alanine on large scale laboratory amounts, with *dl*-alanine, to assure its successfulness as a new method for resolution of racemic forms of α -amino acids and related amino compounds.

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Isolation of an Antibacterial compound, Xanthumin from the leaves of *Xanthium strumarium* Linn.

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XANTHIUM strumarium Linn (Compositae), commonly known as 'Chhota Gokharu' in Hindi and 'Cocklebar' in English is an annual herb which grows wildly throughout India upto an altitude of

l-form in solution
d-form insoluble

It is to be pointed out that interaction of amino-compounds with quinones of the type (I) gives normally the 2,5-disubstituted products and in no case could the monosubstituted products be isolated^{2,3}. However, with racemic forms or with single optically active compounds only monosubstituted quinonoid products are formed under suitable ratios of reactants, probably because the optically active quinonoid molecule of type (II) is chemically less reactive, that it does not react further under the applied reaction conditions. The monosubstituted reaction products (II) were hydrolysed to give pure *d*- or *l*- α -amino acids by refluxing with concentrated mineral acids.

7,000 ft. The plant is used as diaphoretic and sedative. Its root is used as a bitter tonic and in the treatment of cancer and strumous diseases¹.

The seed fat of this plant has been thoroughly investigated by several workers^{2,3,4}. Plourde and Mockle⁵ have isolated Xanthinin from the leaves of Canadian *X. strumarium* while Minnato and Horibe⁶ have reported the isolation of a stereoisomer of Xanthinin from Japanese *X. strumarium* which they named as Xanthumin. No phytochemical work seems to have been done on the leaves of Indian *X. strumarium*, the petroleum ether extract of which was reported earlier to be active against gram positive